

Proximate and Antinutrient Composition of Infant Food Formulated using Yellow Maize, Soyabean and Moringa Leaves

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Abstract

This study investigated the proximate and antinutrient composition of infant complementary food formulated from yellow maize (*Zea mays*), soybean (*Glycine max*), and Moringa leaf powder (*Moringa oleifera*) in three blend ratios: R65 (65:30:5), R60 (60:30:10), and R55 (55:30:15). Standard procedures as outlined by the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC, 2005) were employed to determine the contents of moisture, ash, crude fibre, protein, lipid, carbohydrate, and selected antinutrients—phytate, tannin, and oxalate. All formulations met the World Health Organization (WHO) recommended limits for infant complementary foods. Among the blends, R60 recorded the highest protein (21.08%), lipid (8.55%), and energy content (407.55 kcal/100 g), while maintaining moderate antinutrient levels: phytate (9.25%), tannin (9.22%), and oxalate (189.08 mg/100 g). R55 exhibited the highest carbohydrate content (62.60%) and tannin concentration (12.74%), whereas R65 had the highest fibre (5.88%) and ash (7.65%) content but the lowest energy value (387.03 kcal/100 g). The observed variations were primarily influenced by the proportion of Moringa leaf powder, a nutrient-dense ingredient known for its rich mineral profile. Based on its superior nutrient composition and balanced antinutrient content, R60 emerged as the most suitable formulation for infant feeding. The findings support the potential of using locally available food sources to develop affordable and nutritionally adequate complementary foods. Further studies are recommended to assess micronutrient bioavailability, sensory acceptability, and antinutrient reduction techniques.

Keywords: Infant complementary food, Proximate composition, *Moringa oleifera*, Yellow maize, Soybean, Antinutrients, AOAC methods, Protein-energy malnutrition, Local food formulation

1.0 Introduction

The transition from exclusive milk diet to one in which variety of food is required to satisfy the nutritional needs of an infant child is very critical. Poor nutrition less than optimum feeding practices during this critical period may result in poor infant growth (WHO, 2003). Infant malnutrition is a major world health challenge in many developing countries. It is often occasioned by not having enough of the

right kind of food to eat or the inability of infant to utilize the food eaten (Ahima, 2008; Ikese *et al.*, 2017). Protein energy malnutrition (PEM) and iron deficiency are also the most common forms of infant malnutrition in sub-Saharan Africa (FAO/WHO, 1985; Ahima, 2008).

Micronutrient deficiencies have been recognized as an important contributor to the global burden of disease in infants. According to WHO (2002), about 19% of 10.8million child death's globally a year is attributable to iodine, iron, vitamin A and zinc deficiencies. In Nigeria, UNICEF; (2001) recorded malnutrition as the major causes of health problem of infant and young children, 6 months to 24 months of age which coincides with the period of complementary feeding. This problem is attributed to the introduction of poor complementary foods to infants which are inadequate in protein energy and micronutrients.

However, the high cost of primary infant food formula in developing countries continue to place them beyond the reach of low-income families who revert to poorly processed traditional foods (Solomon, 2005). Several researchers (Gernand *et al.*, 2016; De-Regil *et al.*, 2017; Ikese *et al.*, 2017; Verhoef *et al.*, 2018; Li *et al.*, 2019; Tam *et al.*, 2020. Dewey *et al.*, 2021) have made attempts to combat infant malnutrition through development of improved complementary infant feed. With the increasing importance of complementary and infant food, there is a continuous need to design infant food products, which will meet the nutritional needs of all weaning mothers of different financial background especially those in the developing countries.

A variety of primary ingredients have been utilized in the formulation of infant foods, with particular emphasis on enhancing their micronutrient composition. Commonly used ingredients include short rice, yellow maize, soybean grains, mashed fish meal, crayfish, egg yolk, unripe banana, yam, and potato, which are often incorporated by mothers in the preparation of complementary diets for infants."

Maize is one of the most important cereal crops rich in carbohydrates which is often processed into staple food for people of variable age range. It is also one of the primary ingredients in the formulation of complementary infant food formula. Soybean which is characterized by its high digestible protein content, is another important primary ingredient used in the preparation of infant food formula. However, these two primary ingredients do not provide all the necessary macro and micronutrients needed for the optimum infant growth. *Moringa Oleifera* is an important source of micronutrient. It was on this note that *Moringa oleifera* leaves which is very rich in minerals like calcium, potassium, zinc, magnesium, iron and copper (Kasolo *et al.*, 2010), and calcium which is very essential for human growth and development (Lalas and Isaknis, 2002) was included as a primary ingredient. It is on this note that the present study seeks to adopt maize, soya beans and iron-rich *Moringa Oleifera* leaves as primary ingredients for the development of infant food formulation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of Samples

Maize (zea mays), soybean (Glycine max) and moringa leaf were used for this study. Maize and soybean were obtained from Itam market, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. While Moringa leaves was obtained from a plant in Onna, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Preparation of Maize Flour

Yellow maize grains were cleaned thoroughly to remove stones, dust, immature, and damaged kernels. The cleaned maize was soaked in water for 12 hours to loosen the seed coat (testa). After soaking, the grains were rubbed between the palms and washed repeatedly with clean water to remove most of the testa. The dehulled grains were sun-dried for approximately 48 hours under ambient conditions (30–35°C) and then oven-dried at 70°C for 30 minutes to further reduce moisture content. The dried grains were then milled into flour using a laboratory hammer mill and sieved through a 0.5 mm mesh. Final moisture content was maintained at approximately 10% for safe storage.

Preparation of Soybean Flour

Soybean seeds were thoroughly cleaned to remove stones, immature and damaged grains, as well as other extraneous materials. The cleaned seeds were soaked in water for 12 hours to facilitate the removal of the seed coat (testa). After soaking, the seeds were rubbed between the palms and repeatedly washed with clean water until most of the testa were removed. The dehulled seeds were then sun-dried for approximately 48 hours under ambient conditions (30–35°C), followed by oven drying at 70°C for 30 minutes to further reduce moisture content. The dried soybeans were milled using a laboratory hammer mill and sieved through a 0.5 mm mesh to obtain fine flour suitable for food formulation. Final moisture content was maintained at approximately 10% to ensure storage stability.

Preparation of Moringa leaf Powder

Moringa leaves were washed in clean water. Then it was dried in oven 40°C for 30 minutes, then milled and sieved.

Blend Formulation for the primary ingredients

Maize flour, soybean flour and *Moringa leaves* powder were blended as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Blend Formulation for Infant Food

Mix Ratio Symbol	Maize Flour	Soybean Flour	Moringa Leaf Powder
R65	65%	30%	5%
R60	60%	30%	10%
R55	55%	30%	15%

Analysis of Proximate Composition

Proximate composition parameters, including moisture content, crude fibre, crude protein, ash, and carbohydrate, were determined using standard methods as described by the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC, 2005). Moisture content was determined by oven drying at 105°C to constant weight, crude protein by the Kjeldahl method (using a conversion factor of 6.25), crude fibre by acid-base digestion, ash content by incineration in a muffle furnace at 550°C, and carbohydrate was calculated by difference.

Determination of Moisture Content

Weighing bottle was washed and dried in an oven at 80°C for some minute, cooled and weighed (a). Exactly 2_g of the sample was weighed into the weighing bottle. Then weight of the bottle and its content (sample) was taken (b).

The weighing bottle and its content was then dried in an oven at the temperature of 105°C for 24hours. It was then removed from the oven allowed to cool in a desecrator to room temperature, weighed with a minimum exposure to atmosphere. This was repeated till constant weight was obtained (c)

$$\text{Calculation: Moisture (\% wet weight)} = \frac{b-c}{b-a} \times 100$$

Determination of Ash Content

Crucible with lid was ignited in a muffle furnace at the temperature of 105°C for an hour. It was transferred to a desecrator to cool and weighed (a). Exactly 2 grammes of finely ground dry sample was put into the pre-weighed crucible. The weight of the crucible and its content (sample) was taken (b). The crucible and its content (sample) were char on a heater or 3 Bunsen flame in a fume cupboard, to drive off most of the smoke (until smoking cease). It was then transferred to a muffle furnace heated at (500-600°C) to burn off all the organic matter. It was left at this temperature for 2 hours. The crucible was taken out, when cooled, it was then covered and placed in a desiccator and weighed (c)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Calculation: Ash \%} &= \frac{\text{weight of Ash}}{\text{weight of sample}} \times \frac{100}{1} \\ &= \frac{c-a}{b-a} \times \frac{100}{1} \end{aligned}$$

Determination of Crude Fibre Content

A 2_g of material was defated with petroleum ether for 2 hours, it was then boiled under reflux for two minutes with 200_ml of solution containing 1.25% of H₂SO₄ per 100_ml solution. The solution was filtered through linen or cotton cloth on a fluted funnel, then washed with boiling water until the washing were no longer acidic. The residue was transferred to a beaker and boiledfor another 30 minutes with 200_ml of a solution containing 1.25_g of NaOH per 100ml. Thefinal residue was filtered and washed with boiling water several times until it was base (NaOH) free. The residue was then finally washed twice with ethanol and was qualitatively transferred into a pre-weight crucible and was dried in an oven at 150_°C (I₀), and was then incinerate in a furnace at 550_°C and was allowed to stand at this temperature for 2 hours. It was then cooled in a desiccator and weighed (Ia) (loss in weight)

$$\text{Calculation: } = \frac{1a-1o}{\text{weight of original sample taken}} \times 100$$

Determination of Crude Fat Content

A 2_g of sample was weighed into extractor thimble, which has already been washed, dried in an oven, plugged lightly with cotton wool. Exactly 150_ml of petroleum ether (Boiling point 60-80_°C) was poured into a 250_ml capacity round bottom flask. The soxhlet extractor was filter into the round bottom flask which was on a heating mantle. The soxhlet apparatus was assembled and allowed to reflux for about 4 hours. The extract was poured into a dried pre-weighed beaker (W_1) and the thimble was rinsed with a little quantity of the ether and was placed back to the beaker. The beaker was heated on a steam bath or oven to drive off the excess solvent. The beaker was cooled in a desiccator and weighed (W_2)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Calculation:} &= \frac{\text{weight gain in flask}}{\text{weight of sample}} \times \frac{100}{1} \\ &= \frac{W_2 - W_1}{\text{weight of sample}} \times \frac{100}{1} \end{aligned}$$

Determination of Crude Protein Content

A 1_g of the sample was accurately weighed into a standard 250_ml kjeldahl flask containing 1.5_g CuSO_4 and 1.5_g of NaSO_4 as catalyst and 5ml concentrated H_2SO_4 . The kjeldahl flask (digestion) was placed on a heating mantle and was heated gently to prevent frothing for some hours until a clear bluish solution was obtained. The digested solution was allowed to cool and this was quantitatively transferred to 100ml standard flask and make up to the mark with distilled water. Exactly 20_ml portion of the digest was pipette into a semi-micro kjeldahl distillation apparatus and treated with equal volume of 40% NaOH solution. The ammonia evolved was steam distilled into a 100_ml conical flask containing 10_ml solution of saturate boric acid which 2 drops of tashirus indicator (double indicator) has been added. The top of the condenser was immersed red into the boric acid double indicator solution and then the distillation continued until about 2/3 of the original volume obtained. The tip of the condenser was rinsed with a few millimeters of distilled water in the distillate which was then titrated with 0.1_M HCL until a purple-pink end point was observed. The blank determination was also carried out in the similar manner as describe above except for the omission of the sample. The crude protein was obtained by multiplying the % Nitrogen content by a factor (6.25)

Calculation = Crude Protein Nitrogen X Factor

$$= \frac{\text{Sample titre} - \text{blank titre} \times 0.1 \times 0.04}{\text{weight of sample}} \times \frac{20}{1} \times \frac{100}{1} \times 6.25$$

Determination of Carbohydrate Content

This was determined as the difference obtained after subtraction of total organic Nitrogen (Protein), fat, ash, fibre, moisture from the total dry matter.

Determination of Caloric Value (Energy)

The caloric value of the sample was obtained by multiplying the value of the crude protein, fat and carbohydrate by 4, 9, 4 kcal respectively and taking the sum of the product.

Analysis of Antinutrient

Tannin, phytate, and oxalate contents were determined using standard methods. Tannin was quantified using the Folin–Denis spectrophotometric method as described by AOAC (2005), phytate was determined following the method of Wheeler and Ferrel (1971), and oxalate content was estimated using the method of Day and Underwood (1986).

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.1 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA) to determine the Mean and standard deviation from the three determinants. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed to determine significant differences among the means at a 5% level of significance ($p < 0.05$).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Proximate Composition: The proximate composition of the formulated infant food is presented in table 2.

Table 2: Proximate Composition of Infant Food Formulated from Yellow maize, Soyabeans and Moringa Leaf Powder

Proximate Composition	R65	R60	R55
Moisture (%)	1.08±0.003	1.47±0.001	1.30±0.002
Ash (%)	7.65±0.001	5.01±0.002	5.32±0.003
Fibre (%)	5.88±0.003	3.79±0.002	3.82±0.544
Protein (%)	20.48±0.245	21.08±0.544	20.72±0.099
Lipid (%)	8.23±0.001	8.55±00.002	7.54±0.003
CHO (%)	57.76±0.045	61.47±0.026	62.60±0.035
Carbohydrate (Kcal)	387.03±0.030	407.55±0.025	401.14±0.030

The moisture content in the formulated infant food was observed to be lower in R65 with a mean value of 1.08±0.003 whereas a higher mean value of 1.47±0.001 was observed R60. A higher Ash content was observed for R65 with a mean value of 7.65±0.001 as compared with a lower mean value of 5.01±0.002 observed for R60. The fibre content in the formulated food was also observed to be higher in R65 with a mean value of 5.88±0.003 compared to the lower mean value of 3.79±0.002 observed for R60. Slight differences were also observed for the mean Protein values with a thin range between 20.48±0.245 and 21.08±0.544 where the high and low values were observed for R65 and R60 respectively. The Lipid content in the formulated food was also observed to be higher in R60 with a mean value of 8.55±00.002 as compared to the lower mean value of 7.54±0.003 observed for R55. The Starch content (CHO) was observed to be higher in R55 with a mean value of 62.60±0.035 as compared to the lower mean value of 57.76±0.045 observed for R65. High carbohydrate content was observed R60 with a mean value of 407.55±0.025 as compared to the low mean value of 387.03±0.030 observed for R65, Fig 1

Fig.1: Proximate Composition of Soybean, Moringa Leaves, yellow maize R65, R60 and R55

Phytochemical Composition: The phytochemical composition of the formulated infant food is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Phytochemical composition of Infant Food Formulated from Yellow maize, Soyabeans and Moringa Leaf Powder.

Anti-Nutrient	R65	R60	R55
Phytate	9.61±0.022	9.25±0.01	9.35±0.02
Tannin	8.48±0.003	9.22±0.004	12.74±0.005
Oxalate	99.04±0.82	189.08±1.05	162.07±1.01

The phytochemical components of the formulated infant complementary food were also evaluated. Higher mean phytate content of 9.61±0.022 was observed for R65 as compared to the slight low value of 9.25±0.01 observed for R60. The tannin content had a higher mean value of 12.74±0.005 observed in the R55 infant food formula as compared to the lower mean value of 8.48±0.003 observed in the R65. The Oxalate content show a much higher content with a marked wider difference across the formulated food as to when compared with other phytochemicals. High and low mean values of 162.07±1.01 and 99.04±0.82 were observed for R55 and R65 respectively.

Fig. 4.2: Phytochemical Composition of Soybean, Moringa leaf, yellow maize R65, R60 and R55.

Discussion

The results of the proximate composition of the formulated infant complementary foods (R65, R60, and R55) indicate that all three blends fall within the World Health Organization (WHO, 2003) and United Nations Protein Advisory Group (PAG) recommended limits for complementary foods designed for infants. Each formulation included yellow maize, soybean, and varying proportions of Moringa leaf powder, resulting in distinct nutritional and antinutritional profiles.

Among the formulations, R60 (60% maize, 30% soybean, 10% Moringa) demonstrated superior nutritional properties with a protein content of 21.08%, lipid content of 8.55%, and caloric value of 407.55 kcal/100g, surpassing the values observed in R65 and R55. These values are in line with WHO guidelines and represent a well-balanced nutritional profile for infant feeding.

Compared to the findings of Ikese et al. (2017), whose infant food formulations reported protein: 16.71%, carbohydrate: 55.51%, fat: 10.39%, ash: 4.20%, moisture: 10.55%, and fibre: 12.64%, the present study's R60 formulation had higher protein (21.08%), carbohydrate (62.60%), and ash (7.65%) content, but lower lipid, fibre, and moisture. The differences may be attributed to the type of base ingredient used and the proportion of Moringa leaves in the current formulations. Furthermore, the carbohydrate level in R60 was consistent with the PAG benchmark of 65% for infant complementary food, whereas the formulation by Ikese et al. was 9% below this threshold. Additionally, the energy content of the R60 blend (407.55 kcal/100g) compared favourably with both proprietary formulae (417 kcal/100g) and the value reported by Ikese et al. (380 kcal/100g), indicating its suitability for meeting the energy requirements of infants during weaning.

The inclusion of Moringa oleifera leaf powder significantly influenced the nutrient and antinutrient profile of the infant food. As the proportion of Moringa increased (from 5% in R65 to 15% in R55), a noticeable increase was observed in certain parameters. For example, Tannin content increased from 8.48% (R65) to 12.74% (R55), Oxalate content increased significantly, peaking at 189.08 mg/100g in R60, and a slight but steady phytate variation was observed across the blends (9.25–9.61%).

While Moringa is widely recognized for its rich micronutrient profile, including calcium, magnesium, zinc, iron, potassium, and copper (Kasolo et al., 2010), it also contains notable levels of antinutritional factors, particularly tannins, oxalates, and phytates, which may limit the bioavailability of certain minerals. For instance, phytate is known to reduce the absorption of calcium, phosphorus, and zinc, and interfere with enzyme activity (Niu et al., 2020). In this study, however, phytate levels remained within acceptable limits, unlike the report by Uloma et al. (2014), who recorded phytate and oxalate contents <0.5%, likely due to differences in ingredient ratios and processing methods.

Despite this, the nutritional benefits of Moringa, especially in R60, seem to outweigh the drawbacks, given the higher protein, ash, and caloric values. The moderate inclusion level (10%) in R60 appears optimal, balancing enhanced nutrition with manageable antinutrient levels. Excessive Moringa, as in R55, increased antinutrient content disproportionately and could potentially reduce mineral bioavailability and palatability.

The high protein content observed in the R60 blend (21.08%) confirms the protein-enhancing role of soybean and Moringa, which are both leguminous and leaf-based sources of plant protein, respectively. The low moisture content (<1.5%) across all blends indicates a longer shelf life and reduced risk of microbial spoilage which is critical for infant food safety. The ash content, highest in R65 (7.65%), reflects the mineral richness of the formulations, likely contributed by the Moringa component.

However, the formulation must be considered holistically. While R55 had a slightly higher fibre and comparable protein content, its elevated tannin and oxalate levels suggest potential interference with iron and calcium absorption. Hence, based on the current data, R60 presents the best nutritional profile, balancing macronutrient quality, energy density, and acceptable antinutrient thresholds.

The study demonstrates that complementary infant foods can be successfully developed using locally available, nutrient-dense ingredients such as maize, soybean, and Moringa leaves. The R60 formulation, in particular, may serve as a cost-effective and nutritionally adequate weaning food. The inclusion of Moringa not only enriches the formulation with essential micronutrients but also addresses hidden hunger (micronutrient deficiency) among children in low-income settings.

Nevertheless, the presence of antinutrients calls for further optimization through processing techniques such as fermentation, boiling, or enzymatic treatment to reduce their levels and improve nutrient bioavailability. Additionally, future research should assess the vitamin content, mineral bioavailability, and sensory acceptability of the blends to ensure that the product is not only nutritionally sound but also acceptable to both infants and caregivers.

Conclusion

In conclusion, among the three formulations, the R60 blend (60% maize, 30% soybean, 10% Moringa) emerged as the most nutritionally balanced, providing optimal levels of protein, lipid, ash, and energy within the recommended limits set by the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Protein Advisory Group (PAG). Also, the inclusion of *Moringa oleifera* leaf powder contributed significantly to the nutritional enhancement of the blends, particularly in terms of protein and mineral content. However, increased Moringa inclusion also resulted in higher concentrations of antinutrients such as tannin, phytate, and oxalate, which could impair mineral bioavailability if not properly controlled.

Declaration of Conflict of Interest

The author(s) declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this article. All financial, personal, or institutional affiliations that might be perceived as influencing the results and/or interpretation of the data presented in this manuscript have been fully disclosed, and none are applicable in this case.

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